

In silico study on the carbonic anhydrase activators : Activation of the human cytosolic isozyme III and membrane-associated isoform IV with amino acids and amines

Shalini Singh

QSAR & Cheminformatics Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Bareilly College, Bareilly-243 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : shalinisingh_15@yahoo.com Fax : 91-581-2567808

Manuscript received online 02 February 2014, revised 30 July 2014, accepted 25 August 2014

Abstract : The quantitative structure activity relationships (QSAR) study on the activation of the human secretory isoform of the metalloenzyme carbonic anhydrase hCA III (cytosolic) and IV (membrane-associated) with a series of natural and non-natural amino acids and aromatic/heterocyclic amines are reported. A large set of MOPAC, PRECLAV and DRAGON descriptors have been used to obtain tri parametric models. A heuristic algorithm selects the best multiple linear regression (MLR) equation showed the correlation between the observed values and the calculated values of activity is very good. The obtained models are discussed using a variety of statistical parameters. This work is exploring the structural attributes of bioactive molecules.

Keywords : Carbonic anhydrase activators, hCA III, hCA IV, amino acids, amines, QSAR, PRECLAV.

Introduction

Carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) inhibition with sulfonamides was discovered by Mann and Keilin^{1,2} and its activation by different classes of compounds was reported by Leiner^{3,4}. A multitude of physiologically relevant compounds such as amino acids, oligopeptides or small proteins, as well as many biogenic amines (histamine, serotonin, and catecholamine's among others) were shown to efficiently activate the catalytic activity of isoforms of the metalloenzyme carbonic anhydrase which acts as an efficient catalyst for the inter conversion between carbon dioxide and bicarbonate at neutral pH⁵⁻⁸. The very recent report^{4,9,10} that some carbonic anhydrase activators (CAAs) such as phenylalanine and imidazole administered to experimental animals may produce an important pharmacological enhancement of synaptic efficacy, spatial learning and memory proves that this class of relatively unexplored enzyme modulators may have pharmacological applications in conditions in which learning and memory are impaired, such as for example Alzheimer's disease or aging. One must also mention that it was previously reported that the levels of CA are

significantly diminished in the brain of patients affected by Alzheimer's disease¹¹ and these facts strongly support the involvement of different CA isozymes in cognitive functions⁹⁻¹¹. Unlike the cytosolic CA I, II and III, CA IV was the first extracellular isoform to be discovered. Indeed, this isozyme is associated to plasma membranes in lungs, kidneys, ciliary processes within the eye and several other organs, playing an important function in pH regulation, bicarbonate reabsorption in the kidneys, production of ocular fluid, elimination of CO₂ in the lungs, cerebral blood flow, etc.¹²⁻¹⁵.

The affinity constant (K_{aff}) of an activator for the corresponding CA isoform has been denominated the activation constant (K_A)¹⁶ in order to obtain a measure of the strength for the interaction between enzyme and activator, similarly with the inhibition constant (K_I) which defines the potency of an inhibitor in the enzyme-inhibitor (E-I) complex¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Recent studies with CA III knockout mice showed that CA III to be involved in mitochondrial ATP synthesis²⁰, whereas its levels were found to be significantly decreased in mutant mice lacking the gene SULT1E1, indicating a role of CA III in cystic fibrosis

liver disease^{13,21}. CA III is also considered as one of the proteins involved in oxidative stress response both in liver²² and in skeletal muscle²³, probably acting as a scavenger of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and thus protecting cells from oxidative damage²⁴. CA III seems to play an important role (together with E-cadherin) in disruption of the intercellular barrier associated with the down-regulation of E-cadherin in the laryngopharyngeal reflux disease²⁵.

An activation study of the human carbonic anhydrase (hCA, EC 4.2.1.1) isoforms hCA III (cytosolic) and hCA IV (membrane-associated) with a series of natural and non-natural amino acids with aromatic/heterocyclic amines is reported by Supran *et al.*⁴. The present paper deals with the estimation of the activation constant of hCA III and IV as compared to the data reported earlier which is experimentally measured⁴.

Quantitative structure-property/activity relationships (QSPRs/QSARs) are mathematical models that relate the structure-derived features of a compound to its biological or physico-chemical activity. QSAR (also QSPR) works on the assumption that structurally similar compounds have similar activities. Therefore, these methods have predictive and diagnostic ability. They can be used to predict the biological activity of compounds before the actual biological testing. Thus, QSAR approach saves resources and shortens the process of development of new drugs. They can also be used in the analysis of structural characteristics that can give rise to the properties of interest²⁶. I have attempted to build QSAR models using the MOPAC, PRECLAV and DRAGON software to explore the correlations between the calculated molecular descriptors of some amino acids and amines compounds and their experimental activation constant of the hCA III and IV.

Method and computational detail :

Calibration set :

A group of molecules that contains a known structure and a known value of the activation constant K_A are taken in calibration set to develop a QSAR model. The K_A values in the micro molar (μM) of hCA III and IV (measured experimentally)⁴ were converted in 'A' according to the formula $A = \log (c/K_A)$ where c was taken as 9100

for CA III activators and 7900 for CA activator IV in order to obtain large values of 'A'. The activation constant value 'A' of the molecules under the study spanned a range from 1 to 5 is more suggestive. In the above mentioned study⁴ it has been also observed that amino acids and amines of type **1-18** (Table 1) act as hCA III and IV activators, with variable efficacies, depending on their chemical structure.

Geometry optimization and calculation of descriptors :

The minimum energy geometry for each of the molecule in the calibration set was obtained by the conformational search ability of the Omega v.2.4.3²⁷⁻²⁹ program. The isomeric SMILES notation was used as program input in order to avoid any influences on conformational model generation by presenting 3D seed structures. The omega employs a rule-based algorithm²⁷⁻²⁹ in combination with variants of the MMMF 94. The force field used was the 94s variant of the MMMF_NoEstat²⁷⁻²⁹ includes all MMFF (Merck Molecular force field) terms except coulomb interactions. A more rigorous geometry optimization was subsequently performed by the semi empirical PM6 method³⁰ included in the quantum-mechanics program MOPAC³¹, using the keywords *pm6 pulay gnorm=0.01 geo-ok campking mmok bonds vectors*. These keywords fixed the parameters of geometry optimization. The energy minimized structure was used to calculate different molecular properties, including virtual fragmentation descriptors and whole molecule quantum chemical (global) descriptors. For each molecule over three thousand descriptors were calculated using programs MOPAC³¹, PRECLAV^{32,33} and DRAGON³⁴.

Several criteria were used to reduce the descriptors while optimizing the information content of the descriptors set. Firstly, descriptors with no value for all the compounds were disregarded. Secondly, descriptors of which the value is constant (or near-constant) inside each group of descriptors were excluded. Thirdly, the "significant" descriptors are identified through specific criteria³². The variables having high enough diversity are considered "significant" only if their quality q is high enough.

$$q > 1 \quad (1)$$

where, $q = (1 - \min r^2)/(1 - r^2)$

Table 1. Structural detail of amino acids and amine (1-18) act as CAAs against hCA III and IV

(Here $\min r^2 = 0.01$) and r^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the values of the analyzed descriptor and the values of the dependent property.

The experimental activation constant data of hCA III and IV in the μM (after conversion in 'A') were used as dependent variables in building a QSAR model. The parameters to be calculated are various descriptors that are indicative of molecular structure and used as independent variable. The PRECLAV algorithm^{32,33} was used

for obtaining the parameters and for the statistical analysis as reported earlier³⁵⁻⁴⁴. Stepwise multiple linear regression (MLR), technique was used for the QSAR model development using the entire dataset. Using only the 'significant' descriptors^{32,33}, PRECLAV computes thousands of QSAR equations i.e. multilinear formulas of the dependent property. The program combines successively sets with 2, 3,... k significant descriptors ($1 < k < 11$). A set of descriptors contains only those descriptors which fulfill criteria (2) and are sufficiently low inter-correlated.

$$r_{ij}^2 < N^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

where r_{ij}^2 is the square of Pearson linear correlation between the values of two descriptors present in the same set, N is the number of molecules in the calibration set.

Each set of descriptors has been used to calculate a multilinear QSAR equation of type (3).

$$A = C_0 + \sum C_k \cdot D_k \quad (3)$$

where A is represents a dependent property (here the activation constant defined above), C_0 is the free term (intercept), C_k are the coefficients (weighting factors) of the descriptors, D_k are some significant descriptors and k is the number of descriptors in the set.

The square of Pearson linear correlation r^2 of observed/computed values, the Fisher function F , the standard error of estimation SEE, and the quality function Q are criteria for the quality of prediction for the molecules in calibration set.

$$F = r^2 / (1 - r^2) \cdot (N - k) / k \quad (4)$$

$$SEE = [(\sum \Delta^2) / (N - 1)]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

$$Q = r^2 \cdot (1 - k/N) \quad (6)$$

where k is number of descriptors, N is number of molecules in the calibration set and Δ is difference $A_{\text{obs}} - A_{\text{calc}}$.

The descriptors included in the best (by Q function) QSAR are named 'predictors'. The values predictors are presented in Table 2 for hCA III activators and in Table 3 for hCA IV activators. The relative utility of predictors is computed by the formula (7).

$$U = (R^2 - r^2) / (1 - r^2) \quad (7)$$

where R^2 is the square of Pearson correlation between the observed values and the computed values (using k predictors) and r^2 is the square of Pearson correlation between the observed values and the calculated values (using the $k-1$ predictors, i.e. the QSAR equation without the analyzed predictor).

After computation of U for each predictor, their values are normalized within the range [0-1000]. The predictors with high value of U ($U > 500$) can be considered as high relative utility. These predictors are useful because they correlate well with dependent property and

Table 2. Value of the predictors, observed activation constant (in μM) and their corresponding A value where $A = \log(9100/K_A)$, estimated activation constant (A), hat diagonal, standardized residual, $|RStudent|$ of the calibration set molecules **1-18** of hCA III activators

Compd.	ens	fmd	Mor05m	Obs. K_A (μM)	Obs. (A)	Est. (A)	Std. residual	$RStudent$	Hat diagonal
1	0.5545	7.4253	-1.507	35.9	2.4039	2.595387	-0.6747	-0.661	0.2313
2	0.5631	7.3534	-1.519	1.12	3.9098	3.274949	2.099	2.4433	0.1271
3	0.5484	7.8864	-1.995	34.7	2.4187	2.496494	-0.2605	-0.2516	0.1488
4	0.5561	8.163	-2.005	15.4	2.7715	2.740105	0.1008	0.0971	0.0738
5	0.5436	8.3484	-2.535	13.5	2.8287	2.570705	0.9008	0.8943	0.2172
6	0.5482	8.4121	-2.557	28.7	2.5012	2.851	-1.2195	-1.243	0.2149
7	0.5508	8.0901	-2.087	20.5	2.6473	2.594012	0.1743	0.1682	0.1085
8	0.5506	9.0849	-2.646	19	2.6803	2.443328	0.8183	0.8081	0.1998
9	0.5611	8.7312	-2.23	34.1	2.4263	2.844977	-1.3613	-1.4083	0.0974
10	0.5609	8.869	-2.222	43.2	2.3236	2.671252	-1.1374	-1.1505	0.1085
11	0.5712	7.3735	-0.829	36.9	2.392	2.662514	-1.2206	-1.2442	0.5313
12	0.5661	8.711	-1.892	33.2	2.4379	2.646991	-0.6886	-0.6751	0.1203
13	0.5712	7.4399	-1.804	0.78	4.0669	4.202809	-0.4744	-0.4609	0.2169
14	0.5676	7.185	-1.415	1.03	3.9462	3.587766	1.1974	1.2179	0.1449
15	0.5826	8.1105	-1.565	1.1	3.9176	3.865672	0.1749	0.1688	0.1591
16	0.5961	7.8756	-1.296	0.32	4.4539	4.586935	-0.513	-0.499	0.3582
17	0.589	7.2291	-1.373	0.091	5	4.922212	0.2998	0.2898	0.3576
18	0.5699	10.133	-2.242	36.4	2.3979	1.966592	2.0673	2.39	0.5846

Table 3. Value of the predictors, observed activation constant (in μM) and their corresponding A value where $A = \log(7900/K_A)$, estimated activation constant (A), hat diagonal, standardized residual, $|RStudent|$ of the calibration set molecules **1-18** of hCA IV activators

Compd.	mdn	EEig15r	prm	Obs. K_A (μM)	Obs. (A)	Est. (A)	Std. residual	$ RStudent $	Hat diagonal
1	2.2653	0	0.5816	7.3	3.0343	3.0705	-0.1676	-0.1617	0.094
2	2.2653	0	0.5833	12.3	2.8077	3.072	-1.2225	-1.2465	0.0945
3	0	0	0.6093	36.3	2.3377	2.4951	-0.7517	-0.7395	0.1506
4	0	0	0.5739	49.3	2.2048	2.4641	-1.2309	-1.256	0.1405
5	0	0	0.6173	15.3	2.7129	2.5021	1.008	1.0086	0.1531
6	0	0	0.6188	34.7	2.3573	2.5034	-0.6992	-0.6858	0.1536
7	5.9632	-0.984	0.7907	37.1	2.3283	2.3183	0.0622	0.06	0.5
8	5.9245	-0.984	0.7928	39.6	2.2999	2.3098	-0.0622	-0.06	0.5
9	0	0	0.5745	25.1	2.498	2.4646	0.1585	0.1529	0.1407
10	7.8954	0	0.7878	0.079	5	4.7418	1.729	1.8787	0.5681
11	2.2656	0	0.0174	25.3	2.4945	2.5759	-0.3891	-0.377	0.1507
12	0	0	0.0179	30.9	2.4077	1.9766	2.1411	2.5159	0.2149
13	5.9297	0	0.02	3.14	3.4007	3.5482	-0.7677	-0.7559	0.2842
14	3.7215	0	0.1145	5.19	3.1825	3.0465	0.641	0.627	0.1288
15	4.6225	0	0.0521	7.13	3.0445	3.2303	-0.9078	-0.9017	0.188
16	2.9004	0	0.013	24.9	2.5014	2.7401	-1.1433	-1.157	0.1551
17	3.767	0	0.7152	1.3	3.7837	3.5852	0.964	0.9613	0.1789
18	0	0	0.0389	45	2.2444	1.995	1.2302	1.2552	0.2042

not correlate with other predictors. Each 'useful predictor' offers ample information about the variation in activity from molecule to molecule.

PRECLAV divides the analyzed molecules into virtual fragments using an algorithm reported earlier^{45,46}. The virtual fragments identified by PRECLAV do not always coincide with the classical functional groups. The presence of a significant fragment in the molecule greatly influences the inhibitory activity either in a positive or negative way.

Validation and predictability of the developed model :

The best way to evaluate quality of regression model is leave one out (LOO) cross validation, one object (one biological activity value) is eliminated from data set and data set is divided into subsets (number of subsets = number of data points) of equal size. The cross-validated function r_{cv}^2 is a measure of homogeneity of calibration set from the point of view of predictors' set, i.e. from the point of view of structure-activity relationship. The rank

correlation Kendall⁴⁷ is also used to validate the model.

Once internally validated, the data set (calibration set) was split into reduced calibration set (training set) and validation set (test set) using hierarchical clustering technique⁴⁸ and proceeded to a QSAR study. The quality of the prediction for the external validation was considered as a measure of the quality of the computation method. The external predictive potential of the developed models was judged on the value of predictive r^2 ($r_{pred}^2 > 0.5$)⁴⁹. The r_{pred}^2 parameter is computed by the formula (8).

$$r_{pred}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum [Y_{\text{observed (test)}} - Y_{\text{predicted (test)}}]^2}{\sum [Y_{\text{observed (test)}} - \bar{Y}_{\text{training}}]^2} \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{Y}_{\text{training}}$ is the average value for the dependent variable for the training set.

Applicability of domain and detection of outliers :

Predictive potential of a model on the new data set is influenced by the similarity of chemical nature between calibration set and prediction set⁵⁰. A QSAR model can be used for screening new compounds if its domain of

application is defined^{49,51}. The need to characterize the model applicability domain is also reflected in the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) guidelines for QSAR model validation^{52,53}. QSAR model should only be used for making predictions of compounds fall within the specified domain may be considered reliable. Extent of extrapolation^{54,55} is one simple approach to define the applicability of the domain. It is based on the calculation of the hat diagonal (leverage) h_i for each chemical, where the QSAR model is used to predict its activity :

$$h_i = \frac{1}{n} x_i^T (X^T X)^{-1} x_i \quad (9)$$

In eq. (9), x_i is the descriptor-row vector of the query molecule and X is the $k \times n$ matrix containing the k descriptor values for each one of the n training molecules. A hat diagonal (leverage) value $> 3(k + 1)/n$ leverage warning limit⁵² is considered large.

Outliers are observations that are poorly fit by the regression model. Outlying compounds should not be removed unless a good reason for their removal can be given. The variance of the observed residuals is not constant. This makes comparisons among the residuals difficult. One solution is to standardize the residuals^{56,57} by dividing by their standard deviations. This gives a set of residuals with constant variance. $|RStudent|$ (cross-validated leave one out standardised residuals)^{56,57} is a standardized residual that has the impact of a single observation removed from the mean square error.

To visualize the applicability of domain of a developed QSAR model, William plot was used. In the William plot, $|RStudent|$ versus leverage values (h_i) are plotted. This plot could be used for an immediate and simple graphical detection of both the response outliers and structurally influential compounds in a model. It must be noted that compounds with high value of leverage and good fitting in the developed model can stabilize the model. On the other hand, compounds with bad fitting in the developed model may be outliers. Thus, combination of leverage and the $|RStudent|$ could be used for assigning the applicability of domain.

Results and discussion

The statistical computations were conducted using the specific formulas and procedures of PRECLAV program algorithm³². Using only the “significant” descriptors PRECLAV computes ten thousand QSAR type (3) multilinear equations. The quality of the obtained equation is reflected by the value of the Q function and also by values of some usual statistical functions. During the PRECLAV MLR analysis, I observed that the 3-parametric model has the highest value of the Q function for hCA III and IV activators and also has the highest predictive power as follows :

QSAR #1 for hCA III activators :

Dependent property : activation constant (A) for hCA III

Molecules number in calibration set : 18

Number of “significant” descriptors in presence of prediction set = 1000

$$A = -29.5704 + 67.7976(\text{ens}) - 1.0664(\text{fmd}) - 1.6524 (\text{Mor05m})$$

ens = Sum of [net charge · exposed atomic surface] products (charge < 0) / Molecular surface area ratio ($U = 1000$)

fmd = maximum molecular dimension ($U = 913$)

Mor05m = 3D-MorSE – signal 05/weighted by atomic masses ($U = 771$)

Whereas the quality of correlation is described by the statistical indices :

$$\text{SEE} = 0.2938, r^2 = 0.8851, F = 38.5288, r_{cv}^2 = 0.7835, K = 0.5294, Q = 0.7376$$

SEE = standard error of estimation, r^2 = Pearson square correlation, F = Fisher function, r_{cv}^2 = Pearson cross-validated square correlation (Leave one out method), K = Kendall rank correlation and Q = Quality function.

The high usability of the ens ($U = 1000$) descriptor mostly influences the activation constant of hCA III activators because the utility value of this descriptor is high among the three descriptor in the QSAR model. A posi-

Singh : In silico study on the carbonic anhydrase activators : Activation of the human cytosolic isozyme III *etc.*

tive coefficient for ens descriptor refers to an increment in the activation constant profile of the molecules with an increase in the value of this descriptor as seen in the case of molecules **13**, **15**, **16** and **17**. Similarly, the low range values for the ens descriptor accounts for the reduced activation constant profile of molecules **1**, **3**, **5** and **6**. The negative coefficient of fmd descriptor signifies their influence conducive to the activation constant profile of the molecules. Molecules **13**, **16** and **17** bearing lower order values for this descriptor exhibit enhanced activation constant. The negative coefficient with negative profile of Mor05m descriptor influenced the activation constant and it was confirmed by the most active molecule **16** and **17** in database bearing the high order value of Mor05m.

In this study, molecules of analyzed database include 18 virtual fragments but only four virtual fragments are considered significant [CH_2 ($r = 0.725$), N atom ($r = 0.6888$), CH ($r = -0.5972$) and OH ($r = -0.5892$)]. The percentage in weight of molecular fragments are well correlated in positive or negative way with the values of activation constant. The presence of substituted CH_2 groups (Compound no. **1** to **18**); the presence of N atom (Compound no. **16** and **17**) fragments is favorable to the activation constant. The presence of CH (Compound no. **1** to **11** and **18**) and OH (Compound no. **1** to **10** and **12**, **13**,

18) was found unfavorable to the activation constant.

The minimum correlation descriptor/activity is computed for Mor05m = 0.2478. The minimum intercorrelation between ens/fmd ($r^2 = 0.0576$) and the maximum intercorrelation between descriptors is computed for fmd/Mor05m pair ($r^2 = 0.5044$). So the collinearity between the predictors are not found.

QSAR #2 for hCA IV activators :

Dependent property : activation constant (*A*) for hCA IV

Molecules number in calibration set : 18

Number of "significant" descriptors in presence of prediction set = 1000

$$A = 1.9609 + 0.2647(\text{mdn}) + 1.9457(\text{EEig15r}) + 0.8767(\text{prm})$$

mdn = Minimum distance between nitrogen atoms ($U = 1000$)

EEig15r = Eigen value 15 from edge adj. matrix weighted by resonance integrals ($U = 952$)

prm = Polarity parameter ($U = 669$)

Whereas the quality of correlation is described by the statistical indices :

$$\text{SEE} = 0.2062, r^2 = 0.914, F = 53.1587, r_{cv}^2 = 0.8486, K = 0.7516, Q = 0.7617$$

Table 4. Observed, estimated, residual values hCA III and IV activation constant (*A*) of compounds used in the training set

Compd.	CA III activation constant (<i>A</i>)			Compd.	CA IV activation constant (<i>A</i>)		
	Obs. (<i>A</i>)	Est. (<i>A</i>)	Res.		Obs. (<i>A</i>)	Est. (<i>A</i>)	Res.
2	3.91	3.232	0.678	1	3.034	3.063	-0.029
3	2.419	2.416	0.003	3	2.338	2.499	-0.161
4	2.772	2.692	0.08	4	2.205	2.468	-0.263
6	2.501	2.757	-0.256	5	2.713	2.507	0.206
7	2.647	2.524	0.123	6	2.357	2.508	-0.151
8	2.68	2.388	0.292	7	2.328	2.318	0.01
9	2.426	2.823	-0.397	8	2.299	2.31	-0.011
10	2.323	2.658	-0.335	10	5	4.706	0.294
11	2.392	2.693	-0.301	11	2.494	2.564	-0.07
12	2.438	2.661	-0.223	12	2.407	1.977	0.43
13	4.067	4.159	-0.092	13	3.4	3.517	-0.117
15	3.918	3.905	0.013	15	3.044	3.207	-0.163
17	5	4.937	0.063	16	2.501	2.725	-0.224
18	2.398	2.046	0.352	18	2.244	1.995	0.249

Table 5. Observed, estimated, residual values of hCA III and IV activation constant (*A*) of compounds used in the test set

CA III activation constant (<i>A</i>)				CA IV activation constant (<i>A</i>)			
Compd.	Obs. (<i>A</i>)	Est. (<i>A</i>)	Res.	Compd.	Obs. (<i>A</i>)	Est. (<i>A</i>)	Res.
1	2.404	2.54	-0.136	2	2.808	3.065	-0.257
5	2.829	2.465	0.364	9	2.498	2.469	0.029
14	3.946	3.552	0.394	14	3.182	3.028	0.154
16	4.454	4.662	-0.208	17	3.784	3.571	0.213

SEE = standard error of estimation, r^2 = Pearson square correlation, F = Fisher function, r^2_{cv} = Pearson cross-validated square correlation (Leave one out method), K = Kendall rank correlation and Q = Quality function.

The high usability of the mdn ($U = 1000$) descriptor mostly influences the activation constant of hCA IV activators because the utility value of this descriptor is high among the three descriptor in the QSAR model. A positive coefficient for mdn descriptor refers to an increment in the activation constant profile of the molecules with an increase in the value of this descriptor as seen in the case of molecules **10** and **13**. The positive coefficient with negative value of EEig15r descriptor decreased the activation constant profile of the molecules and it was confirmed by the molecule **6** and **7**. The positive coefficient of prm descriptor influenced the activation constant and it was confirmed by the most active molecule **10** and **17** in database bearing the high order value of prm. In this study, molecules of analyzed database include 18 virtual fragments but only one C_6H_6N ($r = 0.776$) virtual fragment is considered significant. The presence of C_6H_6N (Compound no. **10**) is favorable to activation constant.

The minimum correlation descriptor/activity is computed for prm ($r^2 = 0.0258$). The minimum intercorrelation between mdn/prm ($r^2 = 0.0194$) and the maximum intercorrelation between descriptors is computed for mdn/EEig15r pair ($r^2 = 0.2119$). So the collinearity between the predictors are not found.

External validation, applicability domain and pharmacophore model :

In the present work, the molecules with rank **1**, **5**, **14**,

Fig. 2. Pharmacophore model for QSAR# 1.

16 for QSAR #1 and **2**, **9**, **14**, **17** for QSAR #2 constituted the validation set (test set) and the remaining mol-

Singh : In silico study on the carbonic anhydrase activators : Activation of the human cytosolic isozyme III *etc.*

Fig. 3. Correlation of observed vs estimated K_A in the calibration set and validation set of QSAR# 1.

Fig. 4. $|RStudent|$ of observed vs hat diagonal QSAR# 2.

ecules form the reduced calibration set (training set). The validation set of 04 molecules (22.22% of database) captures all the features and span the activity range of the entire data set. I can assume that the reduced calibration set obtained in this way is a representative sample for the calibration set. In the case when there is a validation set, the most significant tool is the correlation between the estimated and experimental values of QSAR #1 and QSAR #2 for the molecules in the validation set. In the presence of the validation set, we obtained the three parametric models for the reduced calibration set (for 14 molecules) with the predictors used in the above QSAR study and obtain results :

QSAR #1

$$r^2 = 0.8899, F = 32.32, SEE = 0.33447, r^2_{\text{pred}} = 0.90468$$

QSAR#2

$$r^2 = 0.9174, F = 37.045, SEE = 0.2430, r^2_{\text{pred}} = 0.89905$$

I can state that the estimated value for the molecules in the validation set are close to the experimental ones and has ordered the molecules in a sequence similar enough to the real one hCA III and IV activation constant. This one was confirmed by graph (Figs. 3 and 6) between observed and estimated value of calibration set and validation set. The predictive r^2 ($r^2_{\text{pred}} > 0.5$) parameter indicates significant ability of the developed model to predict the activation constant ($\log K_A$) of new compounds.

Fig.5. Pharmacophore model for QSAR# 2.

As discussed earlier, I used $|RStudent|$ of observed activation constant calculated by the obtained models and hat diagonal (leverage) for assigning applicability of domain (AD). Values of leverage could be calculated for

Fig. 6. Correlation of observed vs estimated K_A in the calibration set and validation set of QSAR# 2.

calibration set for hCA III and IV activators shown in Tables 2 and 3. Applicability of domain for the developed model is shown in William plot (Figs. 1 and 4). Influential compounds are points with leverage value higher than the warning leverage limit. It can be seen in the William plot; all molecules in calibration set lie in the application domain of the developed model. None of the molecules have a hat diagonal (leverage) value higher than warning leverage limit (0.666). Molecule 2 and 18 for hCA III and 12 for hCA IV have higher $|RStudent|$ than threshold limit $|RStudent| < 2$ but their leverage are within limit (0.666), so the compounds are not considered the outliers.

The pharmacophore models generated by BROOD⁵⁸ are used to develop and describe the interaction between ligands and the target receptor from the ligand point of view. I have developed a computer representation of the pharmacophore model with most active compound no. 17 for CA III and compound no. 10 for CA IV includes information on the available space at important substituent positions. In Fig. 2 for CA III activator exhibit two pharmacophore elements (one donor and one acceptor) with two cation point. In Fig. 5 for CA IV activator displays five pharmacophore elements (three acceptors and two donors) with one anion point.

Conclusions

Statistically significant linear QSAR models imply the proposal of hCA III and IV activators for : data representation, data modeling and data prediction. The atomic

surface area play dominant role for the hCA III activation constant. The CH_2 and N fragments are favorable for the hCA III activation constant profile. The minimum distance between nitrogen atoms and polarity parameter play dominant role for the activation of hCA IV. The $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}$ fragments are favorable to the hCA IV activation constant profile. QSAR model of hCA III and IV activators can be used in the prediction of activation constant for new compounds which may be important for novel anti Alzheimer's drug.

Acknowledgement

The author (SS) expresses her thanks to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for providing financial support under UGC Research Award No. F.30-29/2011(SA-II). This article is dedicated to the memory of the late Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar (1936-2012).

References

1. T. Mann and D. Keilin, *Nature*, 1940, **146**, 164.
2. A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 284.
3. M. Leiner and G. Leiner, *Biochem.*, 1941, **311**, 119.
4. D. Vullo, I. Nishimori, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *Biorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 4303.
5. S. Pastorekova, S. Parkkila, J. Pastorek and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **19**, 199.
6. I. Nishimori, T. Minakuchi, S. Onishi, D. Vullo, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **50**, 381.
7. I. Nishimori, D. Vullo, A. Innocenti, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *Biorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 5351.
8. J. Singh, B. Shaik, S. Singh, S. Sikhima, V. K. Agrawal, P. V. Khadikar and C. T. Supuran, *Biorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007,

Singh : In silico study on the carbonic anhydrase activators : Activation of the human cytosolic isozyme III *etc.*

- 15, 6501.
9. M. K. Sun and D. L. Alkon, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 2001, **297**, 961.
 10. C. T. Supuran, *Future Med. Chem.*, 2011, **3**, 1165.
 11. W. Meier-Ruge, P. Iwangoff and K. Reichlmeier, *Arch. Gerontol. Geriatr.*, 1984, **3**, 161.
 12. C. T. Supuran, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.*, 2008, **7**, 168.
 13. C. T. Supuran, *Curr. Pharm. Des.*, 2008, **14**, 603.
 14. M. Hilvo, C. T. Supuran and S. Parkkila, *Curr. Top Med. Chem.*, 2007, **7**, 893.
 15. C. T. Supuran, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **7**, 825.
 16. M. Ilies, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran in "Carbonic anhydrase – Its inhibitors Anhydrase – Its Inhibitors and activators", eds. C. T. Supuran, A. Scozzafava and J. Conway, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2004, pp. 317-352.
 17. S. Singh, *Med. Chem.*, 2012, **8**, 656.
 18. A. Thiry, J.-M. Dogné, B. Masereel and C. T. Supuran, *Trends Pharmacol. Sci.*, 2006, **27**, 566.
 19. C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **27**, 759
 20. M. Liu, G. A. Walter, N. C. Pathare, R. E. Forster and K. Vandendorpe, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 2007, **104**, 371.
 21. L. Li and C. N. Falany, *J. Cyst. Fibros*, 2007, **6**, 23.
 22. T. Yamamoto, R. Kikkawa, H. Yamada and I. J. Horii, *Toxicol. Sci.*, 2006, **31**, 49.
 23. U. J. Zimmerman, P. Wang, X. Zhang, S. Bogdanovich and R. Forster, *IUBMB Life*, 2004, **56**, 343.
 24. S. R. Raisanen, P. Lehenkari, M. Tasanen, P. Rahkila, P. L. Harkonen and H. K. Vaananen, *FASEB J.*, 1999, **13**, 513.
 25. G. A. Gill, N. Johnston, A. Buda, M. Pignatelli, J. Pearson, P. W. Dettmar and J. Koufman, *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.*, 2005, **114**, 913.
 26. L. C. Yee and Y. C. Wei in "Statistical Modelling of molecular Descriptors in QSAR/QSPR", eds. M. Dehmer, K. Varmuza and D. Bonchev, Wiley-Blackwell, Germany, 2012, Vol. 2, pp.1-2.
 27. OMEGA (version 2.4.3), OpenEye Science Software, 3600 Cerrillos Road, Suite 1107, Santa Fe, USA, 2010.
 28. G. Tresadern, D. Bemporad and T. A. Howe, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2009, **27**, 860.
 29. T. A. Halgren, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1999, **20**, 720.
 30. J. J. P. Stewart, *J. Mol. Model*, 2007, **13**, 1173.
 31. J. J. P. Stewart, MOPAC2012, Stewart Computational Chemistry, Colorado Springs, CO, USA, <http://OpenMOPAC.net> 2012.
 32. PRECLAV v. 1203 (documentation included) is available from Center of Organic Chemistry – Bucharest, 2012.
 33. L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2005, **56**, 639.
 34. The DRAGON Plus v. 5.5 program is available from Todeschini, R. Talet srl., via V. Pisani, 13-20124, Milano, Italy.
 35. L. Tarko, C. E. Stecoza, C. Ilie and M. C. Chifiriuc, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2009, **60**, 476.
 36. L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2007, **58**, 192.
 37. L. Tarko, S. Avram and D. Mihailescu, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2011, **62**, 371.
 38. R. Done, G. Mandrila and L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2009, **60**, 214.
 39. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, (Under publication) Posted online on February 11, 2014. (doi:10.3109/14756366.2013.864652).
 40. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2013, **21**, 1495.
 41. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **27**, 666.
 42. S. Singh, P. V. Khadikar, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **24**, 337.
 43. S. Singh, *Lett. Drug Des. Discov.*, 2009, **6**, 286.
 44. S. Singh, S. Singh and P. Shukla, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2011, **20**, 1565.
 45. L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2004, **55**, 539.
 46. L. Tarko, *ARKIVOC*, 2004, **xiv**, 74.
 47. T. Andrei and S. Stancu, *Statistica. Ed. All, Bucuresti*, 1995, 341.
 48. N. R. Draper and H. Smith, "Applied Regression Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1981.
 49. A. Golbraikh and A. Tropsha, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2002, **20**, 269.
 50. L. Eriksson, J. Jaworska, A. P. Worth, M. T. D. Cronin, R. M. McDowell and R. P. Gramatica, *Health Perspect*, 2003, **111**, 1361.
 51. D. W. Osten, *J. Chemom.*, 1998, **2**, 39.
 52. OECD document ENV/JM/MONO (2007) 2.
 53. A. P. TI Worth, T. Aldenberg, I. Benjamin, M. T. D. Cronin, P. Gramatica, J. S. Jaworska, S. Kahn, G. Klopman, C. A. Marchant, G. Myatt, N. Nikolova-Jeliazkova, G. Y. Patlewicz, R. Perkins, D. W. Roberts, T. W. Schultz, D. T. Stanton, J. J. M. van de Sandt, W. Tong, G. Veith and C. Yang, *ATLA*, 2005, **33**, 155.
 54. A. Tropsha, P. Gramatica and V. K. Gombar, *QSAR*

- Comb. Sci.*, 2003, **22**, 69.
55. S. Weaver and M. P. Gleeson, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2008, **26**, 1315.
56. NCSS (Statistical Software Delux package), 329 North 1000 East; Kaysville, UT, USA, 2004.
57. R. Dennis Cook, "Residuals and Influence in Regression", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1982.
58. BROOD (version 2.0.0), OpenEye Science Software, 3600 Cerrillos Road, Suite 1107, Santa Fe, USA, 2010.